
EFFECT OF CHILD MARRIAGE ON THE EDUCATION OF THE GIRL-CHILD IN NIGERIA.

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ABSTRACT

The study examined the Effect of Child Marriage on the Education of the Girl-child in Nigeria. Descriptive survey research was adopted for this study. The target population was parents in Nigeria. The stratified random sampling technique was used to select 289 respondents for the study. Instrument titled Child Marriage on Girl-child Education Questionnaire (CMGEQ) was used to collect data for the study. The instrument yielded a reliability index value of 0.85. Descriptive statistics such as frequency count, percentages, mean score, and standard deviation were used to analyse the research questions while inferential statistical tools such as t-test was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The study revealed that poverty, religious/cultural belief, indiscipline, socio-economic background among others were some of the causes of child marriage among girl-child in Nigeria. The study further revealed that child marriage has negative effects on the education of the girl-child in Nigeria. This study therefore recommended that government at all levels should provide free or subsidized education for girls to reduce financial barriers to schooling, counsellors in collaboration with schools should organize awareness campaigns to educate parents, religious leaders and communities about the harmful effects of child marriage on girl-child education and well-being, government should establish alternative education programmes, such as evening classes or vocational training to accommodate girls who dropped out of school due to early marriage and develop livelihood programmes to reduce the economic pressures that often lead to child marriage.

Key Words: Child Marriage, Education and Child-child.

Introduction

Child marriage remains a pressing global issue, disproportionately affecting girls and significantly impeding their access to education. According to UNICEF (2021), child marriage is a formal or informal union where at least one party is under 18 years of age, it is particularly prevalent in low and middle-income countries, driven by poverty, cultural norms and gender inequality. While international efforts have sought to curb the practices, millions of girls continue to be married off at a young age, with severe consequences for their educational attainment.

The institution of marriage as the integral union of a man and a woman for socio-economic, psychological and procreation motive is as old as the history of man on earth. According to Bayisenge (2015), child marriage also known as early marriage is any legal marriage or cohabitation between two parties in which one or both parties is or are below the age of 18 years. However, in sub Africa region, the issue of child marriage is common with female who are physically, physiologically and psychologically ready to shoulder the responsibilities of marriage and child bearing. Elujekwute (2011) stated that child marriage involves either one or both spouses being children and may take place with or without formal registration and under civil, religion or customary laws. Phinney (2008) observed that marriage is primarily meant for people who attained the age of 18 years and above and are physically, socially and psychologically mature, capable of handling social and economic situations. International Centre for Research on Woman (ICRW, 2010) reported that early marriage has many negative consequences on the girl-child as well as the society in which she lives, ranging from educational stagnation, poverty, health care to maternal mortality and among others.

Child marriage is a violation of human rights in general and of girl's rights in particular. Elujekwute (2011) noted that child marriage has profound physical, emotional, intellectual and psychological impacts on the girl-child development. This hinders effective and efficient educational development and productive opportunities of individuals for national growth and development. Bunch (2018) stated that marriage at early age of one's life conflict with his/her academic pursuit. Therefore, married women are bound to achieve less in education or not to continue with formal education. However, every society and culture have some basic norms and beliefs that guide the people. In Northern Nigeria for instance, early marriage of the girl-child is permissible but comes with grave consequences. One of which led to school dropout and gender violence within the marriage union. There is growing evidence that the incidence and prevalence of child marriage is retarding the growth of the girl-child especially those from less-privileged background and thus constituting a stumbling block to the progress of enrolling and retention at both primary and secondary school (Loaiza & Wong, 2012).

Education plays a crucial role in empowering girls, reducing poverty and fostering gender equality. However, child-marriage often disrupts a girl's educational trajectory by imposing household responsibilities, early pregnancies, and social restrictions that hinder school attendance and academic performance (Usman & Musa, 2021). Studies have shown that girls who marry early are significantly less likely to complete their secondary education, thereby limiting their economic opportunities and perpetuating cycles of poverty and inequality (Malhotra & Elnakib, 2021). Child marriage significantly impacts school enrolment and retention rates in Nigeria. Early marriage often leads to school dropouts, truncating the educational aspirations of young girls. According to World Bank (2011), marrying between the ages of 15 and 17 primarily affects secondary education enrolment and retention. Child marriage is widespread in Nigeria; according to Oyekola (2024), the country ranks 10th in Africa with a high rate of child marriage (43% out of 20). The Association for Reproductive

and Family Health (ARFH) asserted that child marriage has an impact on a child's physical development, with consequences including early pregnancy, dropping out of school, health problems, domestic abuse, a lack of empowerment, and social isolation. One of the most agonizing and unsettling issues in Nigeria is child marriage, a practice where parents compel their young children, particularly the female, to marry, sometimes to a complete stranger.

According to UNICEF (2014), out of the 10 countries with the highest rates of child marriage, seven are in Sub-Saharan Africa including Nigeria. It is estimated that 700 million women will be married before age 18 by 2050 and that Sub-Saharan Africa will surpass South Asia on the number and global share of child marriage. Even by doubling the current rate of decline, in 2050, Sub-Saharan Africa will account for 47% of the total child marriage in the world (UNICEF, 2014). This makes focusing on the issue of child marriage critical and important to improving access to quality education for the girl-child. Omotayo (2014) stated that, girls who dropped out of school or not been enrolled in the first place are likely to be pushed into early marriage and this usually prevents them from resuming their education. Bayisenge (2015) stated that child marriage is due to various factors such as, the search for economic survival, protection of young girl, peer group and family pressures, sexuality, wars, civil conflicts, socio-cultural, religious values and controlling female behaviour among others. Early marriage is a violation of girl's human rights as it deprives her from freedom, opportunity for personal development and other rights in the society. This practice stands in direct conflict with the objectives of the Millennium Development Goals (MDGS) such as the promotion of basic education, fight against poverty, the prevention of HIV/AIDS and reduction of maternal mortality rate (UNICEF, 2015). The issue of child marriage in Nigeria has become so frequent that it has become a stumbling block standing on the educational advancement of majority of girls.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of the study is to examine the effect of child marriage on the education of the girl-child in Education. The specific objectives of the study are to:

- i. find of the causes of child marriage among the girl-child in Nigeria.
- ii. examine the effect of child marriage on girl-child education in Nigeria.

Research Questions

The following research questions were raised to guide the study:

1. What are the causes of child marriage among the girl-child in Nigeria?
2. What is the effect of child marriage on girl-child education in Nigeria?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance:

HO₁: There is no significant difference between male and female respondents on the causes of child marriage among girl-child in Nigeria.

HO₂: There is no significant difference between urban and rural respondents on the effect of child marriage on the education of the girl-child in Nigeria.

Conceptual Framework

This session deals with the various concepts of the study.

Child Marriage

Child marriage otherwise referred to as early marriage is the marriage before 18 years of age. The term child marriage is used to refer to both formal marriages and informal unions in

which a girl is given out in marriage before age of 18 (UNICEF 2005). Similarly, UNIFPA (2006) defined child marriage or early marriage as any marriage carried out below the age of 18 years, before the girl is physically, physiologically and psychologically ready to shoulder the responsibilities of marriage and childbearing. Ango (2011) defined child marriage as marriage of an adolescent girl to a matured man or vice-versa and this happens at puberty when the individual is getting matured. The marital age according to Molokwu (2012) is above the age of 18 years, when the individual is physically, socially, academically and emotionally matured to cope with the challenges of marriage. The Nigerian review draft decree put the marriageable age of the girl-child at 18 years. Also, the UNICEF (2001) on the rights of the child recommends that children should not be separated from their parents before 18 years unless it is considered necessary.

The Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination Against Women (CEDAW), the most comprehensive international bill of rights for women, states that any marriage of a child should not have any legal status. The Committee that monitors this convention states further in General Recommendation 21 (Article 16(2)) that the minimum age for marriage for both male and female should be 18 years, the age when “they have attained full maturity and capacity to act”. Most child marriages are arranged and based on the consent of parents and often fail to ensure the best interests of the girl-child. Child marriages often include some elements of force. Kyari and Ayodele (2014) noted that child marriage is the practice of marrying a young girl (generally defined as below the age of eighteen) to an adult. It is a situation where female adolescents and teenagers are married to adult husbands, in these instances, sometimes, the men can be twice their ages and these females become child brides. Delprato and Akyeampong (2017) viewed child marriage as early marriage, which means legal or customary marriage between two people, of whom one or both spouses are below the age of 18.

Causes of Child Marriage in Nigeria

Relative contribution of socio-economic background, indiscipline and cultural values (factors) are some of the causes of child marriage on educational development of the girl-child in Nigeria.

i. Socio-economic Background: Child marriage is believed to have been caused by many factors. According to International Children Emergency Fund (UNICEF, 2010) poverty is one of major factor underpinning child marriage in Nigeria, where poverty is acute, a young girl may be regarded as an economic burden and her marriage to a much older sometimes even elderly man, is a family survival strategy and may even be seen as in her interest. In most instance, the bride’s family may receive gifts from the groom or the groom’s family as the bride price for the daughter. Economic support is also another cause of child marriage. For instance, to give out the girl-child of any age to marriage in search for economic survival of the family, some families used the price money to train male children with the belief that they are the ones to take over the affairs of their family. This practice allowed some female children to get married without secondary education. Njokwu (2013) observed that high rate of poverty in the society has deprived many Nigerian children of their right to acquire quality education and other benefits as citizens of the country. According to the author, socio-economic background of female students; lack of money to pay school fees and afford other educational needs as well as the basic needs in the family contributed significantly to the child marriage among female students. This is one of the reasons why many young female students drop out of school, jumped into early marriage and could not continue with education but found hawking along streets and open places to earn a living.

Low income to cater for the demand of family needs in Nigeria influenced many parents/guardians to abet the girl-child for early marriage.

ii. Indiscipline: The term discipline is defined by Trumers (2008) as respect for rule of law, school rules and regulations as well the maintenance of an established standard of behaviour. This implies self-control, restraint, respect for oneself and among others. A behaviour that contradicts the above becomes indiscipline, disobeying or going contrary to normal behaviour. Zubaida (2011) stated that indiscipline is a major problem among female students in Nigeria. The author maintained that indiscipline among female students results from a combination of factors that are intrinsic and extrinsic. Most young girls abandon education and rush into marriage because of the inability of their family to sponsor their education while some is as a result of immoral behaviour (unwanted pregnancy). Due to high level of poverty most female students who drop out of school for marriage, belief or are convinced that they will continue with their formal education later in life. However, Elujekwute (2011) stated that female education after marriage is dependent on the sympathy of the husband, many husbands are adamant in training their wives either because of economic factor, social or cultural factors. Elujekwute further maintained that even the fortunate women who had the opportunity, find it difficult to combine academic work with marital or domestic challenges. Nevertheless, indiscipline among female students also contributed significantly to the cause of child marriage in Nigeria. Bayisenge (2015) stated that female students who lack moral virtues engaged into premarital sex and become victim of child marriage as a result of unwanted pregnancy. Most of these female students who could not marry, either carry out abortion which claim their lives or they drop out of school to nurse their babies. This has jeopardized opportunities of many young girls to acquire higher education in Nigeria.

iii. Cultural Values: Cultural values is another cause of child marriage in Nigeria. The traditional perception of women in Northern Nigeria for instance affects the girl-child education. However, according to Elujekwute (2011) many ethnic groups in Northern Nigeria are fast moving away from their cultural norms, believe and practices to embrace westernization for meaningful growth and development. In another development, Wegh (2013) asserted that it is the culture of Tiv and Hausa people for instance to give out their girl-child of any age to marriage for economic support of the family. Some families used the money to train their male children with the belief that they are the ones to take over the affairs of their family. Udeozor (2014) stated that traditional perception of women in Nigeria affects the level of attention given to girl-child education, often and times emphasis is laid on educating their male counterpart.

iv. Family Alliances: Marriage is a union between two families and some parents lure their girl-child into marriage in order to consolidate family alliances. According to a report by UNIFPA (2014), some marriages in Africa and Asia are seen as a means of strengthening the relationships between families, while in some cases, the children are betrothed even before birth.

v. Kidnapping: The rising case of insecurity in Africa, and particularly in Nigeria has seen the rise of kidnapping and other criminal vices. This has seen young girls kidnapped on their way to school or at school premises and thereafter forced into marriage by their captives. The case of abduction and eventual forceful marriage and impregnation of some of the Chibok girls in the northern part of Nigeria is a typical example of this (Ben-Kalio, Oguiche and Usman, 2024).

vi. Limited Educational Attainment of Parents: Africa is a continent that is still developing and as such most countries have a significant population that lack educational qualification and form of training. This therefore, exposes them to a lot of societal superstitions and misinterpretations of marriage. As a result, this makes them gullible to any superstition or misconceptions that have been passed down from generation to generation regarding early/child marriage. According to Ogueji-offor (2020), the education of parents greatly affects the timing and type of union.

vii. Limited or Lack of Access to Health Information Services: This is a serious contributory factor to the continuous practice of child marriage. This is because parents who engage in this practice are not fully abreast with the consequences of child marriage on their daughter. These include confinement to household roles, sexual abuse, discontinuation of education, exposure to maternal death, Vesico-Virginal Fistulae (VVF) and sexually transmitted diseases. According to (WHO, 2018), adolescent mothers aged between 10 to 19 are at risk of experiencing eclampsia, systematic infections as well as puerperal endometritis when compared to older mothers.

Effects of Child Marriage on Girl-child Education

The school is the most important institution outside the family involved in socializing young people into all dimensions of adult roles and responsibilities. Many years of schooling has been associated with many positive outcomes, including later age of marriage, healthier and better educated children (Ugboha & Ibuebue, 2019). However, child marriage inevitably denies children of school age their right to the education they need for their personal development, preparation for adulthood, and their effective contribution to the future wellbeing of their family and society. Child marriage has a negative influence on the education of the girl-child. According to Nzenwata (2018), child marriage can cause severe problems like domestic violence, early pregnancy, health risk, social stigma, etc on the girl-child which will in turn affect her education.

Personal development of a girl-child education is aborted when her education is terminated for marriage. This does not only affect the girl but also affects the community and the future generation. According to Klasen and Pieter (2012), child marriage affects female labour force participation in the area of returns when they are not actively employed. Also, Chaaban and Cumingham (2011) stated that female reduction in labour force participation has negative effects on the economic growth of the societies, as well as the women and their families. Child marriage perpetuates the cycle of illiteracy and poverty. Around the world, more girls are enrolled in school than ever before, but these girls are much likely to be married at an early age. However, sadly, school enrolment drops sharply after five or six years of schooling (WHO, 2009). Child marriage often results in girls leaving school, reducing their opportunity to learn and to gain skills that would enable them to start an income generating activity or to find a job. It thereby increases the likelihood of low levels of education and employment (UNICEF, 2011).

Mohammed and Abbati (2021) outlined the negative effects of child marriage on the education of the girl-child:

- (1) **Reduced Enrolment Rates:** in communities where child marriage is prevalent, educating the girl-child may be considered unnecessary, leading to lower enrolment rates.

- (2) Increased Dropout Rates: girls who marry early often become mothers soon after, making it difficult for them to continue schooling due to parenting responsibilities and increased burden of household chores, leaving little or no time for education.
- (3) Disruption of Academic Progress: child marriage interrupts the continuity of education, reducing the chances of completing secondary or higher education. Once the girl-child is out of school, it becomes challenging to re-enroll due to age, stigma or lack of support systems.
- (4) Psychological Effects: child marriage can lead to mental health challenges such as stress, anxiety or depression, which can further affect the girl's ability to focus on or pursue education.
- (5) Economic Consequences: girl-child who drop out of school due to early marriage often miss out on acquiring the skills needed for better job opportunities, perpetuating cycles of poverty.
- (6) Impact on Retention Rate: schools in areas with high rates of child marriage may struggle to retain girls beyond primary school levels, as the societal expectations for marriage often outweighs the value placed on education.
- (7) Wider Social Implications: child marriage limits girls' educational opportunities, which has long-term implications for gender equality, economic development and the empowerment of women.

Girl-child Education in Nigeria

According to UNESCO (2014), Nigeria, Africa's most populous country, has over 200 million people and more than 250 ethnic groups. Although Nigeria has had a National Policy on Education since 1981, it has not been implemented effectively and efficiently due to rapid population growth, insufficient political will, a long period of undemocratic governance, and poor management of scarce resources. Women and girls have been most affected by these negative factors. The national literacy rate for female is only 56%, compared to 72% for male, and in certain states the female literacy, enrolment and achievement rates are much lower. For example, girls' net enrolment in Sokoto, one of the six target states under the UNICEF African Girls' Education Initiative, is 15%, compared to 59% for boys. The most important issue in any country is the number of girls that have access to education and quality of education they receive as measured by levels of retention and performance. Despite several efforts to increase enrolment and reduce gender gap, significant increase in access to education still show declines in the overall proportion of girls enrolled at different levels of education system.

The gender gap has not narrowed across the continent of Africa. Some countries including Nigeria, Zambia, Uganda, Tanzania and many others, though have made significant progress in reducing the gender gap, they still have low enrolment for girls at all levels of education. Overall in sub-Saharan, more than two thirds of eligible children are out of school, a majority of whom are girls (FAWE, 2011). Forum for African Women Educationists (FAWE), a pan African non-government organization, that seeks to promote the education of women and girls in Africa had done a lot to improve the education of the girl-child in Nigeria and other African countries. One of its programmes in Nigeria is the Nigerian Girls into Sciences (NIGIS) which is an action-oriented performance enhancement programme for girls at junior secondary level in Nigeria. Its primary goal is to expand interest, and improve performance in science among Nigerian girls. NIGIS project prompted the development of teaching manual in Learning Science by Doing, based on the syllabus of Junior Secondary science in Nigeria, Learn Science by Doing (LSD) is a guide for teaching integrated science in schools. Education is essential for improving women's living standards and enabling them to exercise

greater voice in decision making in the family the community, the place of paid work and the public arena of politics. Basic literacy and other basic skills are absolutely vital to women's empowerment, and without the skills acquired in secondary education, women cannot obtain better paid employment.

Challenges facing Girl-child Education in Nigeria

Girl-child education has for a long time been influenced by many factors in Nigeria. The complications of the girl-child education start at home. It is at this level in the community that girls are educated differently from boys. The parents, siblings, relatives and even the neighbours see girls to be completely different from boys. They erroneously believe that, boys are more capable, more responsible and more significant to the society than girls. Although both girls and boys are brought up together at home and in the community but the girls are forced to grow up differently through this oppressive socialization (Ben-Kalio, Oguce and Usman, 2024). They are not given equal opportunities as boys to prove their capabilities. As a result, the girls grow up believing that they are completely inferior to boys just because they are girls. The prevalence of gender bias society will continue to bring set back on girl-child education, as well as social discrimination between girls and boys. The previous studies have provided evident that girl-child education suffers from a lot of shortcomings. Some of the constraints facing girl-child education include stereotyped images, negative attitudes of teachers, parents' perception of the value of investing in girl education, poverty, traditions and beliefs (Garba, 2014). Poverty at household level forces the parents to make choices as to which child to enroll in school. Social and cultural attitudes of the parents lead to boys getting favoured while the girls are discriminated against (Grace, 2010).

The girls are compelled by high poverty level to abandon school because of lack of school fees, in favour of their brothers. Cultural practices such as child marriages and initiation rites practiced by some communities in some parts of Nigeria expose the girl-child to life styles not conducive to education. The initiation rites and female circumcision make girls to have attitudinal changes, perceiving themselves as adults ready for marriage. They view school as a place for children and therefore they drop out immediately after initiation rite. Another challenge to girl-child education is teenage pregnancy. This has forced many girls to drop out of schools to go and give birth and look after the young one. Unfortunately, there is no clear policy on readmission of the girl back to school after delivery. Only a small number of girls return to school, about 10% in Nigeria (Oke, 2000).

Consequences of Child-marriage on the Girl-child

Child marriage is capable of affecting the victims in the following ways.

- i. **Increased Maternal and Infant Mortality:** Young mothers face higher risks during pregnancy and childbirth due to physical immaturity. Complications such as obstructed labour can lead to life-threatening conditions. Infants born to these mothers are also at greater risk of neonatal complications (Bante, Habtamu & Ali, 2022). Child marriage often leads to early and frequent pregnancies, increasing the likelihood of health complications such as obstetric fistula. Young brides may also have limited power to negotiate safe sex, heightening their vulnerability to sexually transmitted infections, including HIV (Hossain, Matthew & Adhikari, 2009).
- ii. **Mental Health Challenges:** Child marriage is associated with higher rates of depression, anxiety, and post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD). The abrupt transition into adult roles and responsibilities can be overwhelming for young brides (Gage, 2024). Adolescents in child marriages often miss out on personal growth

- opportunities, leading to lower self-esteem and reduced autonomy. This limitation hinders their ability to make independent decisions and pursue personal aspirations. Apart from this, young girls in early marriages are more likely to experience intimate partner violence and marital rape. The significant age gap between spouses can create power imbalances, making young brides more susceptible to abuse (Hall, Lee & Fernandes, 2020).
- iii. **Limited Education:** Child marriage often leads to the discontinuation of formal education, limiting career opportunities. Girls who marry early are less likely to complete their education, which adversely affects their future employment prospect. Lack of education and skills results in financial dependence on spouses, reducing economic empowerment. This dependence perpetuates the cycle of poverty and limits women's ability to contribute economically (Amin, Rahman & Sarker, 2022).
 - iv. **Low socio-economic Status:** Child marriage contributes to intergenerational poverty as young couples often struggle financially due to lack of education and job opportunities. This struggle affects not only the couple but also their offspring, perpetuating poverty. Young brides, particularly women, have limited access to employment, affecting national economic growth. Their absence from the workforce reduces the available talent pool and hinders economic development (Rao, Nair & Singh, 2024).
 - v. **Social repression:** Child marriage reinforces traditional gender roles and discrimination against women. It perpetuates the notion of women as subordinate, limiting their roles to domestic spheres. Young brides may be cut off from peers, support networks, and social opportunities. This isolation can lead to feelings of loneliness and depression (Santos & Capellan, 2023).
 - vi. **Violation of Human Rights:** Child marriage is considered a violation of human rights under international laws, such as the Convention on the Rights of the Child (CRC) and the Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination Against Women (CEDAW). It infringes upon the rights of children to health, education, and freedom from exploitation (United Nations, 2023). In some countries, legal systems do not fully protect children from early marriage due to cultural or religious norms. This lack of protection allows the practice to continue despite its known harms.

Research Design

Descriptive survey design was adopted for this study. This survey design describes a given state of affairs at a particular time (Robson, 2012). It permits the gathering of information through the use of questionnaire from a population based on appropriate sampling techniques. Also, descriptive survey research was considered suitable since it would solicit for information on the problem under investigation from the respondents.

Population of the Study

The population of the study comprised of all parents in Nigeria. Although the exact population of parents in Nigeria are unknown, the population of the study was therefore put at unknown.

Sample Size and Sampling Procedure

A sample size of 289 parents were randomly selected for the study. The sample technique for this research was stratified random sampling where the respondents were selected principally because of the status as parents. They were selected based on gender and location as they were available during the period of the administration of the instrument for this research.

Instrumentation

The instrument for the study was the researchers' structured instrument titled: Child-marriage on Girl-child Education Questionnaire (CMGEQ). The instrument was a 14-items questionnaire designed along a modified 4-point Likert scale to elicit the opinion of respondents with respect to the topic under study.

Validity and Reliability of the Instrument

The instrument was subjected to validations to ascertain the face, content and constructive validity by two experts in the Departments of Counselling and Educational Foundations (Measurement and Evaluation) in the Faculty of Education, University of Abuja. To ensure the reliability of the instrument, the researchers conducted a pilot test using ten (10) parents in FCT, Abuja, who were not participating in the main study. After an interval of two weeks, the researchers further re-administered the same instrument to the same set of respondents and their responses correlated. Using Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (PPMCC) and came up with an index of 0.85, which shows that the instrument was reliable for the study.

Data Collection Procedure

The researchers make use of the services of research assistants who were adequately briefed on their expected roles of administering the instrument to the respondents. The research assistant explained each statement to the parents who are unlearned and indicate by filing in their responses.

Method of Data Analysis

In analyzing the instrument, frequency count, mean scores, percentage and standard deviation were used for the demographic data and research questions. The mean rating of the response was that response with a mean of 2.50 or above was considered agreed and response that had a mean score of less than 2.50 was considered disagreed. t-test was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance.

Demographic Data

In this section, data on gender and location were analysed.

Table 1: Distribution of Respondents based on gender

Gender	Frequency	Percentage
Male	119	41.18
Female	170	58.82
Total	289	100.00

Table 1 shows that the number of male respondents was 119 (41.18%) while the female were 170 (58.82%). This means that there are more female participants in the study than the male.

Table 2: Distribution of Respondents based on Location

Location	Frequency	Percentage
Urban	218	75.4
Rural	71	24.6
Total	289	100.00

Table 2 shows that the number of urban respondents was 218 (75.4%) while the rural respondents were 71 (24.6%). This means there were more urban participants in the study than the rural respondents.

Research Question One: What are the causes of child marriage among the girl-child in Nigeria?

Table 3: Causes of child marriage among the girl-child

S/N	Statements	Mean	Std. Dev	Decision
3.	Pressures from family and community	3.33	0.92	Agreed
4.	Myths and misconceptions about child marriage	2.72	1.07	Agreed
5.	Insecurity has resulted to the occurrence of child marriage	3.27	0.68	Agreed
6.	Indiscipline (premarital sex) contributed to the causes of child marriage	3.11	1.05	Agreed
7.	The cultural practices contribute to child-marriage of the girl-child	3.41	0.89	Agreed
8.	Socio-economic background as a result of lack of funds and other educational needs	2.86	0.86	Agreed
	Sectional Mean	2.80	1.06	Agreed

Table 3 showed the causes of child marriage of the girl-child in Nigeria. The respondents agreed in all items. The sectional mean score of respondents of 2.80. This shows that all the above-mentioned statement in table 3 are the causes of child marriage among the girl-child in Nigeria.

Research Question Two: What are the effects of child marriage on girl-child education in Nigeria?

Table 4: Effects of child marriage on girl-child education

S/N	Statements	Mean	Std. Dev	Decision
9.	Child marriage deprives the girl-child of qualitative education	2.59	0.76	Agreed
10.	Child marriage affects girl-child retention in school	2.89	1.16	Agreed
11.	Child-marriage truncates the girl-child and can lead to reproduction of poverty from one generation to the other	2.97	1.21	Agreed
12.	Child marriage can negatively affect excellent academic performance of female students	2.98	0.96	Agreed
13.	Limited career opportunities	2.67	1.01	Agreed
14.	Child marriage leads to social isolation thereby reducing the girl-child exposure to new learning opportunities and personal growth.	3.12	0.78	Agreed
	Sectional Mean	2.76	1.04	Agreed

Table 4 showed the effect child marriage on the education of the girl-child in Nigeria. The respondents agreed in all items. The sectional mean score is 2.76 showed that the respondents agreed that child marriage have negative effect on girl-child education.

Test of Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance.

HO₁: There is no significant difference between male and female respondents on the causes of child marriage among girl-child in Nigeria.

Table 5: Two-tailed t-test result in respect of male and female parents' responses on the causes of child marriage among girl-child in Nigeria.

Gender	N	\bar{X}	S.D	Df	t-value	Std. Error	Sig@0.05	Decision
Male	119	2.79	1.02	289	0.315	0.151	0.753	Not significant
Female	170	2.74	1.05					

Result on Table 5 showed that there was no significant difference between male and female parents on the causes of child marriage among girl-child in Nigeria ($p= 0.753$, which is greater than 0.05 level of significance). As a result, the first hypothesis was accepted. In other words, the opinion of male and female parents on the causes of child marriage among girl-child in Nigeria are not obviously different.

HO₂: There is no significant difference between urban and rural respondents on the effect of child marriage on the education of the girl-child in Nigeria.

Table 6: Two-tailed t-test result in respect of rural and urban parents on the effect of child marriage on the education on the girl-child in Nigeria.

Location	N	\bar{X}	S.D	Df	t-value	Std. Error	Sig@0.05	Decision
Urban	218	2.72	1.06	289	0.315	0.159	0.481	Not significant
Rural	71	2.83	1.01					

Result on Table 6 showed that there was no significant difference in the responses of urban and rural parents on the effect of child marriage on the education of the girl-child in Nigeria ($p= 0.481$, which is greater than 0.05 level of significance). As a result, the second hypothesis was accepted. In other words, the opinion of urban and rural parents on the effect of child marriage on the education of the girl-child are not obviously different.

Summary of Findings

The following findings have been made in this study.

1. The study discovered that poverty, religious/cultural belief, indiscipline, socio-economic background among others were some of the causes of child marriage among girl-child in Nigeria.
2. The study revealed child marriage has negative effects on the education of the girl-child in Nigeria.
3. The study found no significant difference between male and female parents on the causes of child marriage among girl-child in Nigeria.
4. The result showed that the response of urban and rural parents did not differ significantly on the effect of child marriage on the education of the girl-child in Nigeria.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this work, the following recommendations were made;

1. **Promote access to Quality Education:** government at all levels should provide free or subsidized education for girls to reduce financial barriers to schooling.
2. **Community Sensitization and Advocacy:** counsellors in collaboration with schools should organize awareness campaigns to educate parents, religious leaders and communities about the harmful effects of child marriage on girl-child education and well-being. Counsellors should also engage community leaders as advocates for girl-child education and role models for changing harmful cultural norms.
3. **Reintegration Programmes for Married girls:** the government should establish alternative education programmes, as such evening classes or vocational training to accommodate girls who dropped out due to early marriage. With the help of trained counsellors, provide psychosocial support and counselling services to help married girls return to school and rebuild their confidence.
4. **Introduce Economic Support for Families:** offer financial incentives, such as conditional cash transfers or scholarships to families that keep their daughters in school. Also develop livelihood programmes to reduce the economic pressures that often lead to child marriage.

REFERENCES

- Amin, S., Rahman, L. & Sarker, M. (2022). The Impact of Early Marriage on Economic Empowerment: A Longitudinal Study. *Journal of Gender Studies*, 31(4), 512-528.
- Ango, R. G. (2011). The. Impact of Girls' Education on Early Marriage, Independent Evaluation Report: CAMIFED and CAMA Programmes Zimbabwe.
- Association for Reproductive and Family Health (n.d.). Impact of Early Marriage on the Girl-child. *ARFH Publications*.
- Bante, A., Habtamu, T. & Ali, S. (2022). Maternal and infant mortality risks associated with early marriage: A systematic review. *Global Health Journal*, 15(2), 112-125.
- Bayisenge, J. (2015). Early Marriage as a Barrier to Girls Education: A Development of the Evidence on Consequences of Adolescence Childbearing in developing Countries. Workshop on Adolescent Sexually and Reproductive Health.
- Ben-Kalio, T. F., Oguche, T. E. & Usman, M. B. (2024). Influence of Early Marriages on Girl-Child Enrollment, Retention and Progression in Secondary Schools in Nigeria. *Research Journal of Humanities and Cultural Studies*, 10(4), 139-152.
- Bunch, M. (2018). The conflict between early marriage and academic pursuits. *Educational Review Quarterly*, 32(1), 78–85.
- Chaaban, J. & Cunningham, W. (2011). Measuring the Economic Gain of Investing in Girls: The Girl Effect Dividend, Policy Research Working Paper. Washington, DC: World Bank.
- Delprato, M. & Akyeampong K. (2017). The Effect of Early Marriage timing on Women's and Children's Health in Sub-Saharan Africa and Southwest Asia. *Ann Glob Health* 2017;83:557e67.
- Duflo, E. (2024). Adolescent Girls and Early marriage: Implications for Autonomy and Decision-Making. *Development Economics Review*, 39(1), 89-105.
- Elujekwute, E.C. (2011). Evaluation of Early Marriage on Educational Development of Female Students in Senior Secondary Schools in Makurdi Local Government Area of Benue State (Unpublished PGDE Project) Department of Educational Foundation, Faculty of Education, Benue State University, Makurdi, Benue State-Nigeria.
- Fathima, R., Ramaswamy, S. & Gopal, N. (2022). The Socio-Economic Impact of Early Marriage on Women's Financial Independence. *International Journal of Social Policy*, 28(3), 205-223.
- Forum for African Women Educationists (2011). Strategies for Advancing Girls' Education in Africa. *Nairobi: FAWE*.
- Gage, A. J. (2024). Psychological Distress and Early Marriage: Understanding the Mental Health Burden on Adolescent Brides. *Journal of Child Psychology*, 41(3), 312-327.

- Garba, J.A (2014). Factors Militating Against the Enrolment and Retention of Girl-Child Students in Junior Secondary Schools in Kaduna State. Being a Published Thesis Submitted to Department of Educational Foundation and Curriculum, Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria in Partial Fulfilment of the Requirement for the Award of the Masters Degree in Education.
- Grace, E.T. (2010). Girls Child Education: Rising to challenge. *African Journal of Reproductive Health*, 14(3): 107.
- Hall, J., Lee, S. & Fernandes, R. (2020). Domestic Violence and Child Marriage: Examining the Risk Factors. *Journal of Family Studies*, 29(2), 177-198.
- Hossain, M., Matthew, Z. & Adhikari, A. (2009). Early Marriage and Reproductive Health Risks in Developing Countries. *World Health Organization Report*.
- Klasen, S. & Pieter, D. (2012). The Gender Gap in Labour Force Participation: The Role of Early Marriage. *Economic Development Review*, 19(1), 78-94.
- Kyari, G. V. & Ayodele, J. (2014). The Socio-economic Effect of Early Marriage in North Western Nigeria. *Mediterranean Journal of Social Sciences*, 5 (14). 582-592.
- Lloyd, C. B. & Mensch, B. (2023). Gender Norms and Social Repression: The Constraints of Early Marriage. *Gender & Society*, 37(2), 192-211.
- Loaiza, E. & Wong, S. (2012) *Marrying too Young. End Child Marriage*. United Nations Population Fund; UNFPA, New York.
- Malhotra, A. & Elnakib, S. (2021). 20 Years of the Evidence Base on What Works to Prevent Child Marriage: A Systematic Review. *Journal of Adolescent Health* 68.
- Mohammed, A. & Abbati, H. (2021). Early Marriage and School Dropout Rates among Adolescents Girls: A Case Study of Northern Nigeria. *African Journal of Education and Development*, 29(3), 267-284.
- Njokwu, C. (2013). Socio-Economic Factors Influencing Girl-child Education in Nigeria. *International Journal of Education and Research*, 1(10), 1–10.
- Nzenwata, C.B. (2018). Negative Effect of Early Girl-Child Marriage on Nigeria: The Way Forward. *International Journal of Scientific and Research Publications*, 1(10).
- Oguejioffor, C. N. (2020). Early Marriage and its Impact on Girl's Education in Abakaliki Education Zone of Ebonyi State. *Unizik Journal of Educational Research and Policy Studies*, 1(1), 1-19.
- Oke, M. (2000). Gender Gap and Access to Secondary School Science Education: The way forward. *WAEC Monthly Seminar Paper*, 2:103-113.
- Omotayo, T. O (2014). Women Education in Africa: Gender and Domestic Decision in Africa. *Journal of Sociological Issues in Africa (JSIA)*, 12(5), 242-260.

- Oyekola, O. O. (2024). Perceived Effects of Early Marriage on Academic Achievement among Girls in Oyo State. *NIU Journal of Educational Research*, 10(2): 73-79.
- Oyekola, A. (2024). Nigeria's High Rate of Child Marriage: Causes and Consequences. *African Journal of Gender Studies*, 12(1), 99–112.
- Phinney, H. M. (2008). Consent and Coercion: Examining unwanted Sex among Married young Women in Vietnam. *International Family Planning Perspectives*, 34(4), 165-173. <https://doi.org/10.1363/ifpp.34.165.08>
- Santos, M. & Capellan, T. (2023). Social Isolation and Early Marriage: Examining Psychological Consequences. *Journal of Social Issues*, 39(2), 250-265.
- Sperling, G., Winthrop, R. & Badawy, A. (2022). Girls' Education and Child Marriage: A Critical Policy Perspective. *Brookings Institution Policy Paper*.
- Trumers, J. (2008). Discipline and Academic Performance in Secondary Schools. *Educational Management Review*, 22(3), 45-59.
- Udeozor, R. K. (2014). Girl-child Education: A Spring Board for Enhancing Women Productivity in Nigeria. *Journal of Social Justice for Women Development (JSJWD)*, 2(1), 165-181.
- Ugboha, G. O. & Ibuebue, S. N. (2019). Effect of Early Marriage on Girl-Child's Further Education in Okpokwu Local Government Area, Nigeria: Implications for Counseling. *KIU Journal of Humanities*, 4(1): 65-72
- UNESCO. (2014). Gender Equality in Education: Progress and Challenges. *UNESCO Education Report*.
- UNFPA. (2006). In Ending Child Marriage, A Guide for Global Policy Action International Planned Parenthood Federation and the Forum on Marriage and the Rights of Women and Girls. U.K.
- UNICEF (2014). Early Marriage: A Harmful Traditional Practices. A Statistical Exploration, New York United States of America. www.unicef.org/publications/paf/digest.pdf retrieved on 25th July, 2015.
- UNICEF. (2011). The Impact of Child Marriage on Education and Economic Development. *UNICEF Report on Child Protection*.
- UNICEF (2005). Early Marriage: A Harmful Traditional Practice. UNICEF: New York, USA. www.unicef.org/childmarriage
- United Nations (2023). Ending Child Marriage: Strategies for Global Action. *United Nations Human Rights Report*.
- Usman, M. & Musa, A. (2021). The Consequences of Early Marriage on Girl Child Education in Geidam, Yobe State, Nigeria. *Journal of Research in Humanities and Social Science*, 9 (6), 69-82.

Wegh, A. S. (2013). Introduction to some Basic Cultural Practices in Nigeria, Makurdi; Aboki Publishers

World Health Organization (2009). The Health Risks of Early Marriage and Adolescent Pregnancy. *WHO Policy Brief*.

Zubaida, S. (2011). Beyond Islam: A New Understanding of the Middle East. 10.5040/9780755610624.